

A LITRARY REVIEW ON: ARSHA AS HAEMMORRHOIDS**¹*Dr. Kshama S. Dhamankar, ²Dr. Dnyaneshwar D. Chavan**¹P.G. Scholar, Final Year (Department of Shalya Tantra)²Associate Professor, (Department of Shalya Tantra)Dr. G.D. Pol Foundation's Y.M.T. Ayurvedic Medical College and Hospital, P.G. Institute-
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Article Published on 01 Feb. 2026<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18426591>***Corresponding Author****Dr. Kshama S. Dhamankar**P.G. Scholar, Final Year (Department
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Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra, India.**How to cite this Article:** ¹*Dr. Kshama S. Dhamankar, ²Dr. Dnyaneshwar D. Chavan. (2026). A Litrary Review On: Arsha As Haemorrhoids. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(3), 01-13. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.**ABSTRACT**

'Arsha' is an ailment that affect all economical groups of population. Among all the ano-rectal diseases, Arsha seems to be an entity, which was very clearly known to the ancient Ayurvedic authorities, which simulates the clinical picture of haemorrhoids. According to Ayurveda According to Ayurveda the disease comes under the heading of Mahaagada because it has four major qualities attributed to Maharoga, which are Maramshraya Dirghakalanubandhi, Dushchikitsya and Tridosha involvement. Main characteristic feature of Arsha is sprouts like growth in the ano-rectum. All Ayurvedic literature described that the Arsha is difficult to cure and trouble to the patients like as enemy. The term haemorrhoids is popularly used to refer for pathological varicosity of the haemorrhoidal veins due to increased pressure, is usually caused by straining during defecation, chronic constipation or diarrhoea, pregnancy etc. The main complaints of piles are bleeding, pain and

prolapsed pile mass. Acharyas has given four types of treatment for management of Arsha which is Bsheshaj, Kshar-karma, Agni-karma and Shastra karma.

KEYWORDS: Arsha, mahaagada, dushchikitsya, Dirghakalanubandhi, Haemorrhoids.**INTRDUCTION**

Arsha is sprouts like growth at any where on body (ex. Nasarsha, Vartmarsha, Twagarsha, Lingarsha etc.) but here we consider arsha as hemorrhoid (Gudarsha). Arsha seems to be an

entity, which was very clearly known to the ancient Ayurvedic authorities, which simulates the clinical picture of haemorrhoids. Hemorrhoids are the common problem now a days due faulty lifestyle follows. The symptoms of hemorrhoids are pain during defecation, swelling of anus, bleeding and burning pain during defecation, constipation, abdominal discomfort.

Ayurveda is giving the ideal way of living. Arsha is mentioned in all classical text book of Ayurveda. According to Ayurveda the disease comes under the heading of Mahaagada because it has four major qualities attributed to Maharoga, which are Maramshraya Dirghakalanubandhi, Dushchikitsya and Tridosha involvement. Although hemorrhoids are a common condition diagnosed in clinical practice, many patients are too embarrassed to seek treatment. Consequently, the true prevalence of pathologic hemorrhoids is not known. In addition, although hemorrhoids are responsible for a large portion of anorectal complaints. All Ayurvedic literature described that the Arsha is difficult to cure and trouble to the patients like as enemy. Symptoms of Arsha is clinically resemble as feature of piles. Maximum concepts are similar to each other. Haemorrhoids may be 'internal' or 'external', based on their position above or below the dentate line respectively. Arsha is caused by improper diet, prolonged standing, and faulty defecation habits, which can disrupt the tridosha, particularly the vata dosha. A effect of this disease is induced weakness, decrease the energy and excitement of patients. Important causes of piles are sedentary life, irregular diet and psychological disturbances like anxiety and depression etc. Ayurveda is considered to be the best alternative treatment for hemorrhoids because it addresses the root cause of the disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

All sorts of references have been collected from our ancient ayurvedic texts viz., Sushruta Samhita, Charaka Samhita, Ashtanga Hridaya, Ashtanga Samgraha, Madhav Nidan Samhita, Madhukosh tika. Modern books like A manual on Clinical surgery S. DAS, SRB'S manual of Surgery, Manipl manual of surgery are used as literary source.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To examine the material on Arsha in Ayurvedic texts and modern text, on the causes, types, clinical features, clinical examination and management for Arsha.

NIRUKTI

अरिबत् प्राणान् शृणातत तिनस्ति इतत अर्शः। (मधुकोष)

The disease which hurt like an enemy is called Arsha. Piles are derived from Latin word pila

and it means ball like structure in the anal region. The term haemorrhoids consist of Greek word Haima (blood) and Rhoos (oozes/flowing). It means the disease where blood flows per rectum is called as Haemorrhoids.

DEFINITION

अर्शः-अरिवत्प्राणान् शृणातीत्यर्शः । अरिवत्
प्राणिनो मांसकीलने निविशन्ति यत् । अर्शासि
तस्मादुच्यन्ते गुदमार्गनिरोधतः ॥ (वाग्भटः)

अर्शासीत्यधिमांसविकाराः (चरकः)

The arsha is broad concept can conclude all types of pedunculated growth on skin of Nasa, guda etc.

“दोषास्त्वङ्मांसभेदांसि सन्दूष्य विविधाकृतीन् ।

मांसाङ्कुरानपानादौकुर्वन्त्यर्शासिताञ्जगुः ॥”

(माधवः)

An abnormal sprout like growth occurs in guda, which is torturing to the patients like an enemy and create an obstruction of anal passage is called Arsha.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY^[1]

The vascular hemorrhoids are caused by straining at defecation. When intra- abdominal pressure rises and anal sphincter relaxes, it forms a high pressure gradient. The physiological venous dilatation of plexus is caused by excessive straining. The development of hemorrhoids on straining in the presence of relaxed sphincter causes the reverse flow of blood circulation forcing it into the superior hemorrhoidal plexus. Once it occurred the further reversal is prevented by the closer of valves of superior rectal venous radicals which results dilatation of hemorrhoidal plexus.

NIDAN OF ARSHA^[20]

तत्रानात्मवतां

यथोक्तैः प्रकोपणैर्विरुद्धाध्यशनस्त्रीप्रसङ्गो-

त्कटुकासनपृष्ठयानवेगविधारणादिभिर्विशेषैः प्रकुपिता दोषा एकशो द्विशः समस्ताः

शोणितसहिता वा यथोक्तं प्रसृताः प्रधानधमनीरनुप्रपद्याधो गत्वा गुदमागम्य प्रदूष्य

गुदवलीर्मासप्ररोहान् जनयन्ति, विशेषतो मन्दाग्नेः, तथा तृणकाष्ठोपललोष्ठवस्त्रादिभिः
शीतोदकसंस्पर्श- नाद्वा कन्दाः परिवृद्धिमासादयन्ति, तान्यर्शासीत्याचक्षते

॥(सु. नि. 2/4)

Charaka and Sushruta's perspectives were merged by Vagbhata. Followings are some general categories for the aetiology.

- Based on dietary characteristics, including excessive or inadequate intake of incompatible diets like Guru, Madhura, Sheeta, Abhishyandi, etc.
- Based on Habits: Excessive straining, excessive sexual indulgence, or the repression of natural desires.
- Based on local irritant factors such as improper seating, unlevelled or harsh chairs, and prolonged vehicle rides. According to Mandagni-Arshas, Grahani and Atisara are mutually causal.
- Based on therapeutic abuses, such as excessive oleation therapy, ineffective evacuation therapy, inappropriate Vastikarma administration, etc. The detailed causal factors have been portrayed in Nidana of Arsha Charaka.
- Sahaja Arshas is accountable for the guardians' bad behaviour and past actions. Sushruta also establishes the role of the foolish Ahara and Vihara in the origin of Arshas. The opinions on both Charaka and Sushruta were solidified by Vagbhata.
- Poorly planned arrangements for vastikarma, etc.
- Using a hereditary component Sahaja arsha's aetiology has also been interpreted as having a hereditary component.
- Several causes—pregnancy, etc.

LOCATION^{[2][3]}

सर्वेषां चार्शासां क्षेत्रं गुदस्यार्धपञ्चमाङ्गुलावकाशे त्रिभागा- न्तरास्तिस्तो गुदवलयः क्षेत्रमिति ।

सर्वेषां चार्शसामधिष्ठानं मेदो मांसं त्वक् च ॥

(च. चि. 14/6)

तत्र स्थूलान्तप्रतिबद्धमर्द्धपञ्चाङ्गुलं गुदमाहुः ।

तस्मिन् वलयस्तिस्तोऽधर्धाङ्गुलान्तरसम्भूताः

प्रवाहणी विसर्जनी संवरणी चेति। (सु. नि. 2/5)

Arsha situated at Four and half angula inside from external anal orifice. Adhishthana of arsha is meda, mansa, twaka at three gudavali (pravahani, visarjani, savarani)

- There are three prominent cushions^[24] (Primary Hemorrhoid occur here)
 - Left lateral
 - Right posterior
 - Right anterior

Located at the 3, 7 and 11 o'clock position when patient is lying in lithotomy position.

Most of hemorrhoid occurs at this position.

- Secondary haemorrhoid may be cause among this primary locations.

TYPES OF ARSHA

Arsha's classification

1. According to the source- Arsha basically comes in two varieties.

- Sahaja Arsha (Congenital Hereditary)
- Kalaja (which means one gained after birth.)

2. According to characteristics of bleeding

- Ardra (Sravi) - Pitta and Rakta Dosha pradhan -bleeding piles.
- Shushka - Vata and Kapha Dosha Pradhan - non-bleeding piles.

3. According to site

- Bahya (Samvarani),
- Abhyantara (Visarjini, Pravahani),

4. Based on the prognosis

- Sadhya (Healing)
- Yasya, second (Palliative)
- Asadhya (Incurable)

LAKSHAN OF ARSHA^[2]

According to ayurvedic perspective:- doshaj lakshan

Vataj

“त्र मारुतात् परिशुष्कारुणविवर्णानि विषममथानि कदम्ब

निपुष्पतुण्डिकेरीनाड़ीमुकुलसूचीमुखाकृतीनि च भवन्ति। तैरुपदुतः सशूलं संहतमुपवेश्यते, कटीपृष्ठपार्श्वमेढ्रगुदना- करता भिप्रदेशेषु चास्य वेदना भवन्ति, गुल्माष्ठीलाप्लीहोदराणि एवं चास्य तन्निमित्तान्येव भवन्ति, कृष्णत्वङ्नखनयनदशनवदन वर्ण व मूत्रपुरीषश्च पुरुषो भवति ।“ (सु. नि. 2/10).

Dry, hard, painful, usually of external origin, various shapes, with irregular surface of various colours of fleshy masses, frequently associated with constipation, and painful defecation which is radiating in nature.

Pittaj

पित्तानीलाग्राणि तनूनि विसर्पीणि पीतावभासानि यकृ प्रकाशानि शुकजिह्वासंस्थानानि यवमध्यानि यकृ प्रकाशानि शुकजिह्वासंस्थानानि यवमध्यानि जलोको 3 वक्त्रसदृशानि प्रक्लिन्नानि च भवन्ति । तैरुपदुतः सदाहं सरुधिरमतिसार्यते, ज्वरदाहपिपासामूर्च्छाश्चास्योपद्रवा भवन्ति, पीतत्वङ्नखनयनदशनवदनमूत्रपुरीषश्च पुरुषो भवति ।। (सु. नि. 2/11)

Usually small in size, bluish red in colour, moist fleshy masses of various types, which enlarges during straining with passage of blood mixed with stool, may cause severe burning sensation during defecation which may lead to thirst, faintness and shock.

Kaphaj

श्लेष्मजानि श्वेतानि महामूलानि स्थिराणि वृत्तानि स्निग्धानि पाण्डूनि करीरपनसास्थिगोस्तनाकाराणि, न भिद्यन्ते न स्त्रवन्ति कण्डूबहुलानि च भवन्ति । तैरुपदुतः सश्लेष्माण- मनल्पं मांसधावनप्रकाशमतिसार्यते, शोफशीतज्वरारोचका- विपाकशिरोगौरवाणि चास्य तन्निमित्तान्येव भवन्ति, शुक्ल- त्वङ्नखनयनदशनवदनमूत्रपुरीषश्च पुरुषो भवति ।। (सु. नि. 2/12)

Wide based, smooth, oval, fixed, fleshy masses which generally do not bleed or suppurate and accompanied by severe pruritus and mucous discharge.

Raktaja

रक्तजानि न्यग्रोधप्ररोहविदुमकाकण्टिकाफलसदृशानि पित्तलक्षणानि च, यदाऽवगाढपुरीषप्रपीडितानि भवन्ति तदाऽत्यर्थं दुष्टमनल्पमसृक् सहसा विसृजन्ति, तस्य चातिप्रवृत्तौ पञ्चात्मा शोणितातियोगोपद्रवा

भवन्ति । (सु. नि. 2/13)

Fleshy masses with immense blood loss during defecation, leading to secondary anaemic condition.

Sannipataj

सतिपातजातन सवशदोषलक्षणयुक्तातन ।

(सु. तन. 2/14)

Mixed Lakshana of all Doshas.

Sahaj

सहजानि दुष्टशोणितशुक्रनिमित्तानि, तेषां दोषत एव प्रसाधनं कर्तव्यम् । विशेषतश्चैतानि

दुर्दर्शनानि परुषाणि पाण्डूनि दारुणान्यन्तर्मुखानि । तैरुपदुतः कृशोऽल्पभुक्

सिरासन्त- तगात्रोऽल्पप्रजः क्षीणरेताः क्षामस्वरः क्रोधनोऽल्पाग्निप्राणः परमलसश्च तथा

घ्राणशिरोऽक्षिनासाश्रवणरोगवान्, सतत- मन्त्रकूजाटोपहृदयोपलेपारोचकप्रभृतिभिः

पीड्यते ॥ (सु. नि. 2/15)

Genetically determined ugly appearance. Patient is mostly immunocompromised.

According to modern - Loss of appetite, anal pain, constipation problems, bodily oedema, anxiety, headache, vomiting, lethargy, rectal bleeding, back pain, and emaciation are among the main clinical symptoms of Arsha.

Arsha's stages^[15]

Grade I: Prolepses absent. merely noticeable blood vessels.

Grade II: Prolepses appear when pressing in but diminish on their own.

Grade III: Prolepses when bearing down and manual reduction is necessary.

Grade IV: Prolapsed and unable to be decreased manually.

EXAMINATION OF ARSHA^[14]

1. Inspection- The second degree haemorrhoids are only visible at the anal verge when the patient strains. While the third degree piles are readily recognized as a prolapsing mass in the outer part covered with skin, the inner portion with red or purple coloured anal mucosa, and the junction being marked a linear furrow.

2. Palpation: Per rectal examination on the early stages of piles, they are soft and collapsible on quite impressible examination. But with chronicity and repeated attacks of the thrombosis the subcutaneous connective tissue undergoes fibrosis and then the piles are palpable as a soft longitudinal fold to the palpating finger on per rectal examination.
3. Proctoscopy
4. Sigmoidoscopy
5. Colonoscopy
6. Barium enema

COMPLICATIONS^[15]

1. Profuse haemorrhage
2. Strangulation
3. Thrombosis
4. Ulceration
5. Gangrene
6. Suppuration or abscess formation
7. Fibrosis
8. Perianal haematoma

TREATMENT OF ARSHA AT AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE (FOURFOLD MANAGEMENT)

1. Bheshaj Chikitsa

"तत्र,

अचिरकालजातान्यल्पदोषलिङ्गोपवाणि भेषजसाध्यानि।" (सु. चि. 6/3)

“तत्र भेषजसाध्यानामर्शसामदृश्यानां तु भेषजं भवति।” (सु. चि. 6/3)

Prevention of constipation- Laxative- Gandharva haritaki churna, Triphalachurna, Panchsakarchurna, etc. depending upon the Koshtha of the patient.

Deepan Pachan- Chitrakadivati, Lavanbhaskar churna, Agni tundivati, etc.

Arshoghna

- Rasa - Arshakuthar rasa.
- Vati – Kankayan vati, trifala guggul, arshoghni vati.

- Churna – Nagkeshar churna, lodhra churna, panchasakar churna
- Asava/arishta – Abhayarishta, takrarishta, dantyarishta.
- Taila – Kasisadi taila, jatyadi taila.

Hot sitz bath- Tankan bhasma, Sphaticbhasma, Triphalakwath, Panchawalkalkwath, etc.

Rakta Stambhak- Bolbaddhras, Bolparpati, Kukkutandtwak bhasma, Pravalpisthi etc.

Vranropak- Jatyadi tail, Nirgundi tail, etc.

Vednahara- Madhuyastyadi tail, Triphala guggulu, etc.

- This treatment can be done in GRADE 1 hemorrhoid.

VYATYASAT CHIKITSA

व्यत्यासान्मधुराम्लानि शीतोष्णानि च योजयेत् ।

नित्यमग्निबलापेक्षी जयत्यर्शः कृतान् गदान् ॥(च. चि. 14/243)

Acharya Charaka mention vyatyasat chikitsa in treatment of arsha it is done by using MADHURA – AMLA Dravya and SHIT – USHNA Dravya to reduce arsha vikara.

2. Kshar karma

" मृदुप्रसृतावगाढान्युच्छ्रितानि क्षारेण ।"

(सु. चि. 6/3)

Kshar is a caustic chemical, alkaline in nature obtained from the ashes of medicinal plants.

The Arsha which are soft, extensive, deeply situated, projectile are treated by Kshar. Pittaja and Raktaja varieties should be treated by Mrudu Kshar.

- This treatment can be done in GRADE 1 and GRADE 2 hemorrhoid.

3. Agni Karma

"कर्कशस्थिरपृथुकठिनान्यग्निना ।"

(सु. चि. 6/3)

It is an important Para surgical method and is still used extensively in surgical practice in modified form by way of electric heat cautery and freezing.

Direct treatment of any lesion by Agnikarma is regarded superior than other surgical and

parasurgical measure because of its capacity to destroy the diseased tissues completely and its wide applicability even of lesions incurable by other measure.

Agnikarma is indicated in rough, fixed, broad and hard types of masses and mainly in Vataj and Kaphaj Arsha.

Those patients suffering from prolapsed and third degree piles can be treated with Agni.

Agni karma is contraindicated in Raktaj and Pittaj type of Arsha.

- This treatment can be done in GRADE 1 and GRADE 2 hemorrhoid.

4. Shastrakarma

"तनुमूलान्युच्छ्रितानि क्लेद- वन्ति च शस्त्रेण।" (सु. चि. 6/3)

Shastrakarma is indicated in pedunculated, big, and discharging Arshas.

The preoperative measures should be well taken. The Chedana Karma of Arsha should be done with the help of sharp instruments like Mandalagra, Karapatra, Nakhashstra, Mudrika, Utpalapatra and Ardhadhara in shape of semilunar incision.

After Chedana Karma, if needed, Agnikarma should be immediately applied in case of any remnant or to arrest the active bleeding or secondary oozing of the blood vessels. The procedure of Kavalika placement followed by the Gophana Bandha should be performed.

This whole procedure seems like conventional open haemorrhoidectomy or to say the ligation and excision procedure performed in recent times.

- This treatment can be done in GRADE 3 and GRADE 4 hemorrhoid.

5. Rakta prayog

छागान्तराधि तरुणं सरुधिरमुपसाधितं बहुपलाण्डु।

व्यत्यासान्मधुराम्लं विदशोणितसंक्षये देयम् ॥(च.चि. 14/209)

According to Charaka in rktarsha where profuse loss of blood use of blood this can be correlated with after anaemia developed due to chronic PR Bleeding can be given blood transfusion.

Treatment of Piles at Modern Perspective^{[12][15][16]}

The treatment of haemorrhoids can be divided into 3 parts according to their degree and local

condition.

1. Medical Treatment
4. Para Surgical Treatment
3. Surgical Treatment

1. Medical Treatment

No specific treatment is available, rather symptomatic treatment is adopted which contains wide range of antibiotics, NSAIDS, laxatives, haemostatic agents, antihistaminic drugs, steroidal treatment, local anaesthetic applications and local antiseptic lotions and ointments.

2. Para surgical Methods^[15]

1. Injection Treatment (Sclerotherapy)
2. Barron Band Ligation
3. Infra-Red Coagulation
4. Anal Dilatation
5. Cryo Surgery
6. Laser therapy
7. Radio frequency coagulation
8. Ultraoid
9. Bipolar dithermy
10. Doppler guided haemorrhoidal artery ligation

Surgical Treatment

1. Open haemorrhoidectomy
2. Closed haemorrhoidectomy
3. Stapled haemorrhoidectomy

RESULTS

Arsha is very prone to erect position results in very high pressure on the valveless rectal venous plexus causing dilatation of hemorrhoidal plexus. Which appears at Guda region which is Sadyapranahara Marma. Ayurveda has effective para surgical treatment over Arsha. Ayurveda is considered to be the best alternative treatment for hemorrhoids because it addresses the root cause of the disease.

DISCUSSION

Haemorrhoids is an common condition, affecting approximately 10 million people per year. It

is difficult to pinpoint the evident etiological factors for the dilatation of rectal or anal vein for the manifestation of piles.

CONCLUSION

Arsha is a very terrible condition, patient is afraid of defecation because of pain with bleeding per rectum. Moreover, patient becomes very anxious after observing pan full of blood. Thus, Ayurveda definitely has immense potential to manage all stages of Arsha successfully without any complications. Ayurveda literature are the same as modern science. Acharyas described a unique order in the management of arshas, they are Bsheshaj, Kshara, Agni and Shahstra chikitsa.

Ayurveda has given better planning to avoid immediate surgery.

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